

Socio-Economic Analysis of Slum Dwellers: A Case of Cuttack District, Odisha

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ABSTRACT

The socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers does not allow them to live healthy life. They do not have access to sanitation and they cannot get a safe water supply. They have to live in adverse conditions due to poor social, economic, and health facilities. The main purpose of this study was to find out the socio-economic condition of slum dwellers in Cuttack, Odisha. To analyse the socio-economic conditions three objectives have been considered that is to study the changing pattern of social needs of slum dwellers, to examine the change in magnitude of the economic condition of slum dwellers, and to study the employment opportunity and livelihood of the slum dwellers in the study area. Data were collected from 100 households in five slums of the city where respondents were selected by simple random sampling method. To analyse the hypothesis this study used a partial t-test to calculate the significance of the variables namely annual income, food expenditure, health expenditure, education expenditure, and distance covered for bringing water. The study found that people living in slums are in a very vulnerable state. No doubt their economic conditions were improving but bad hygienic conditions and the health status of households were also not at a satisfactory level.

Keywords: Slum Dwellers, Health, Education, Employment, Livelihood

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I INTRODUCTION

Rapid population increases and unplanned growth create an urban sprawl with negative economic, social, and environmental consequences. Slums exist worldwide and especially in developing countries are the manifestation of urbanisation and consequent unplanned urban development. The world's urban areas are highly varied. Still, many cities and towns are facing problems such as a lack of jobs, homelessness and expanding squatter settlements, inadequate services and infrastructure, poor health and educational services, and high levels of pollution. Urbanisation occurs mainly because people move from rural areas to urban areas, resulting in growth in the size of the urban population and the extent of the urban regions. Rapid urbanisation, industrialisation, rural migration, poverty, and inadequacy of resources are the principal factors of slum formation. So here we can define a slum area as those areas where people living in poverty, have less equipment for primary needs, sanitation, fewer opportunities for personal development, inaccessible basic amenities, etc. Even there is less opportunity for

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overall development. The growing number of slums, squatter settlements, and pavement dwellings in the major cities of the third world and especially in India obviously point out to the virtual incapability of the governments to provide shelter to the increasing population. In 1960, the global urban population was 34% of the total; however, by 2014 the urban population accounted for 54% of the total and continues to grow. By 2050 the proportion living in urban areas is expected to reach 66% (UNDESA, 2014). In developing countries, urbanisation usually occurs when people move from villages to settle in cities in hope of gaining a better standard of living. Migration is influenced by economic growth and development and by technological change (Marshall et al., 2009) and possibly also by conflict and social disruption. It is driven by pull factors that attract people to urban areas and push factors that drive people away from the countryside. Employment opportunities in cities are one of the main pull factors. Many industries are located in cities and offer opportunities of high urban wages. There are also more educational institutions providing courses and training in a wide range of subjects and skills. People are attracted to an urban lifestyle. All of these factors result in both temporary and permanent migration to urban areas. Poor living conditions and the lack of opportunities for paid employment in rural areas are pushing factors. People are moving away from rural areas because of poor health care and limited educational and economic opportunities as well as environmental changes, droughts, floods, lack of availability of sufficiently productive land, and other pressures on rural livelihoods.

The dimension of the slums is presumed as something that is deteriorating urban areas that is densely populated and contains dilapidated housing, often in multiple occupation, poverty, social disadvantage and other forms of physical and social deprivation. In addition to the above, development of slums, dynamics of slum formation, all are synonymous to industrialization and urban growth. Nearly 15 percent of the population of Odisha lives in urban areas. With growing urbanisation people from rural areas are migrating to cities in search of livelihood. Every year their number has been increasing which demands habitations with basic infrastructure. The increasing urban homelessness, poverty and poor quality of living of people in slums have been a matter of concern for inclusive urban development. Filthy drains, contaminated water, garbage heaps, damaged roads, choked sewers are a common sight in almost all the slums in the city. Cuttack is yet to offer a healthy life to its slum dwellers. While many of the slums do not have proper roads or drainage systems in place, a majority of the inhabitants do not have access to safe drinking water. Hundreds of people residing in the slums of Cuttack suffer from diseases like cholera, diarrhoea, dengue, malaria and various gastroenteritis diseases every year due to the unhygienic surrounding and contaminated water. Cuttack being close to the capital city Bhubaneswar has attracted a lot of people whether it's for job opportunity of different facilities and therefore we tend to find slum formation in many overcrowded areas where basic amenities like water, drainage etc. are lacking. Therefore, it is time to make a serious attempt to study the problems and how it could be mitigated.

II REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In order to analyse the inter and intra-migration and also the socio-economic strata of the slum dwellers of Gandhi Nagar slum Ali and Toran (2003) found most of the slum dwellers have migrated from the southern part of the city. On the basis of income and expenditure, the socio-economic conditions of the people were not

good. Houses were well built concrete structures. Basic amenities, drainage, water supply, and street lighting were good. But they face the problem of a lack of libraries. The studies showed that the majority of the migrants have come to this particular area because of cheap accommodation. Similarly, Agarwal and Taneja (2005) examines how increasing urbanisation resulted in faster growth of the slum population. The study observed disparities among slums regarding various factors for the health of the children. The study concluded by suggesting the identification, mapping, and assessment of all slums as important factors for the location of missed-out slums. Another suggestion was provided regarding urban child health programs by stating that the health programs should be conducted to improve the health of the slum children. In studying the socio-economic factors like; living conditions, physical environment, households' health behaviour particularly dietary practice and health outcome of Dhaka city by Akhter (2008), found out that the reason behind this is the unhealthy environment through the statistical technique, frequency distribution. With the objectives to know the poor health condition and high prevalence of diseases among children in the slum with an implication with food security. In such circumstances, ensuring food security of urban poor is a challenge if their socio economic condition remains like this only. The study shows that high prevalence of disease among children reveals inadequate education or lack of consciousness among parents to give proper care to the children. The study found that the majority of them can't afford nutritious food which was expensive to them, socio economic factors like income, expenditure and education were influencing food security in slums.

With the objective to know about the issue of upward mobility, migration and livelihood of the slum dwellers this study examines importance of various informal channels through which urban jobs are accessed. This study by Mitra (2009) found that although there are some certain improvements in the well-being of migrant workers over time, several of the long-duration migrants and natives in the cities still lead a low-quality life. Further, Yasmin, (2012) identified the nature of occupational mobility and examine the determinants that support of slum dwellers this paper tries to find out whether this occupational mobility is also observed in case of an urban slum dweller who migrates from his native place in search of earning opportunity, with a hope to improve his livelihood condition, and earn more than that he is earning at his native place. To analyse occupational mobility, the real wages of workers has been calculated after adjusting it for inflation, using national average Consumer Price Index. To analyse the causes and motives of migration of slum dwellers, and their mobility within informal sector and from informal sector to formal sector this paper studies that it is the higher current money income in the town compared to that in rural native places has significant role to play in the migration process of workers from rural areas to the towns informal sector. From the survey it has been found out that the majority of workers have migrated due to poverty, inadequate income, and unemployment and underemployment, natural calamities and social oppression Mohapatra (2013).

To know the issues concerning living conditions and health status in notified and non-notified slums the methodology of slum condition index has been considered. This study by Sajjad (2014) found that social conditions, health conditions and environmental condition index are the outcome factors of poor economic conditions of sampled slums. Slum condition index based approach can be utilised for assessing welfare programmes and relative status in slums, and providing a holistic framework for a healthy city. Damse (2015) with the objectives to study the causes

for the increase of the slums and slum population and also to understand the problems of the slum population this paper found out that problems like famine, drought, limited financial resources, big families etc. contribute towards pushing the rural youth to the urban areas in search of livelihood. Also, the rapid industrialisation and urbanisation attract these rural youth to relocate to the urban areas in search of employment for livelihood.

To study the informal settlements and health conditions and sanitation of women in Nairobi, Kenya Corburn and Hildebran (2015) found that inadequate urban sanitation adversely affects the social determinants of women's health in slums. The impacts on women's health include infectious and different chronic diseases, food contamination and malnutrition. And, Marimuthu et al., (2016) examined the reasons for the underutilisation of available public health facilities and to compare the difference with non-slum areas of the major metropolitan cities of India this study found in Mumbai slums about 90 per cent of the households are having water sources from public tap or piped to yard followed by Hyderabad having better water supply and Chennai slum dwellers having minimum access to good water sources. About 11.4 per cent of the households do not know where their toilet drainage is connected. Proportions of open defecation is compared among five cities and it is found that Delhi and Hyderabad have similar proportion 75 per cent to 79 per cent, Kolkata and Chennai have parallel high proportion, that is more than 95 per cent and Mumbai 89.6 per cent.

III RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The scope of this study is vast, as it provides a clear picture about the socio-economic conditions of slum dwellers, what types of problems they are facing and under which circumstances they are residing there. This study has a broad scope for researchers, academicians and policy makers to work on, to understand the living condition of the slum dwellers.

IV OBJECTIVES

1. To study the changing pattern of social conditions of slum dwellers in the study area.
2. To examine the change in the magnitude of the economic condition of slum dwellers in the study area.
3. To study the employment opportunity and livelihood of the slum dwellers in the study area.

V DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In Cuttack, some slum localities have high population density. In this study the data has been collected from five slum areas. The five areas have been derived from slum list available namely Gadagadia slum (GA1), Deer park slum (DE2), Bidanasi slum (BI3), Tala sahi slum (TA4) and Markat nagar slum (MA5). These slums are emerging as one of those developing slums in Cuttack. Sample slum households have been selected for the detailed survey to gather the required data and information. Simple random sampling design has been adopted for selection of representative localities and households. The data collections are solely based upon the primary data of 100 households which is basically both quantitative and qualitative in nature. For example, a comprehensive and structured household

questionnaire is prepared for the household survey in the slums and Focus Group Discussions or direct personal interview is conducted among males and females to understand the living condition of slum dwellers. Appropriate statistical tools were used to analyse the field survey data. In order to analyse the hypothesis this study used partial t test to calculate the significance of the variables namely annual income, food expenditure, health expenditure, education expenditure, distance covered for bringing water.

VI RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Based on the field survey data the socio economic conditions of the slum dwellers in Cuttack district, Odisha has been discussed in the subsequent sections. In order to analyse the hypothesis this study used partial t-test to calculate the significance of the variables namely annual income, food expenditure, health expenditure, education expenditure, and distance covered for bringing water.

Table-1 shows the age distribution of the sample households of five slums. The age group is divided into four categories ranging from, less than 15 years to above 55 years of age.

Table 1: Age groups wise distribution of sample households

Slum code	Age group distribution (in %)				Total
	Below 15	15-35	35-55	Above 55	
GA-1	5	25	55	15	100
DE-2	0	10	85	5	100
BI-3	20	20	60	0	100
TA-4	10	20	45	25	100
MA-5	5	60	25	10	100

Source: Field survey

Table 2: Religious Status of sample households

Slum code	Religion (in %)	
	Hindu	Christian
GA-1	90	10
DE-2	NA	100
BI-3	100	NA
TA-4	100	NA
MA-5	100	NA

Source: Field survey

Table-2 shows that, out of the total proportion of sample households in Gadagadia slum 10 per cent of households are Christian and the rest 90 per cent are Hindu. In the other four slums the total population are Hindu so basically all these slums are Hindu dominated slums. And, Table-3 depicting majority of the population are married followed by the unmarried category.

Education plays a vital role in the socio economic condition of people. Education is an important input for the skill and knowledge empowerment among rural communities. It helps for the assessment of productive employment in future. Proper education leads to a good lifestyle and provides awareness of everything. Here in the Table-4 the distribution of educational status among sample households has been shown.

Table 3: Marital status of sample household

Slum code	Marital status (in percentage)					Total
	Unmarried	Married	Widowed	Divorced	Separated	
GA-1	12	78	4	NA	6	100
DE-2	13	75	12	NA	NA	100
BI-3	15	70	5	10	NA	100
TA-4	2	82	10	3	3	100
MA-5	35	65	NA	NA	NA	100

Source: Field survey

Table 4: Distribution of educational status among sample households

Slum code	Educational status (in %)					Total
	Illiterate	Primary	Secondary	Higher secondary	Degree	
GA-1	10	45	5	10	30	100
DE-2	25	30	20	25	0	100
BI-3	10	30	0	40	0	100
TA-4	50	25	15	10	0	100
MA-5	5	0	20	15	60	100

Source: Field survey

It has been found out from the survey that the Markat Nagar slum is in a better off position than the other four slums, where 60 per cent of people from the total population are degree holders and only 5 per cent people are illiterate (Table-4). In this area people are more educated because they are aware about the importance of education. Because a good education leads to a better environment. Education level of the people in backward areas in general, slum dwellers in specific is an important factor influencing improvement in their lifestyle.

Occupation is generally an activity which means especially as a means of earning a living. From the survey, it has been found that the occupational status of slum dwellers has increased in recent times. And this is due to the implementation of NULM. For an instance let's talk about Markat Nagar slum, before there were 30% labourer 50% house maid and 20% kuli from the total sample households. Now after the implementation of NULM they got more job opportunities and got engaged in occupations like house painter, carpenter etc. besides this slum in other four slums the occupational status has also increased.

The government is providing many programmes to improve the conditions of the slum dwellers. From the above table we can see that the slums are getting benefited by various programmes like SBM, PDS, PMAY, AMRUT, NULM, PMUJ which is basically for sanitation, providing ration card, housing, employment opportunity and electricity facilities. From the above table it can be observed that the Market nagar slum is in a better position than others as it is benefitted by all the given programmes implemented by the government. The Tala sahi slum only got the housing facility by the AMRUT scheme, for them a flat is made. The condition of the other three slums is quite better than this Tala sahi slum.

In the recent scenario (during the field survey), the conditions have improved than before. But that's in the case of male population only. Here the employment opportunity, availability of working days has increased in the case of male population only. That's because in most of the households the female population only does the household work and they are not engaged in any type of occupation. But the wage rate has increased for both male and females. Some of the females are

maids and as there is a demand for house maids in today's world their wage rate increased than before.

The average of each household income has increased than before and that's because of employment programmes provided by the government. From all these analyses we can see that the economic conditions of households are improving. The average family income of every household has increased. That's because people are engaged in different occupations to improve their household conditions.

The majority of people were depending upon wells and rivers as a source of water. But in the recent scenario the municipality is providing water to some households.

From the field survey it was found that, the percentage of people availing drainage facilities has increased. But in Tala sahi slum there is no drainage facility whereas in the Market nagar slum each and every household are availing the drainage facility. In Bidanasi slum the percentage remained constant i.e. 30 per cent of people have drainage system and 70 per cent don't have that. And, in the other two slums the percentage of having drainage facilities has significantly increased.

The field work illustrated that, the majority of people are disposing of the waste in front of the house and in the river. The people are throwing it in an improper way due to negligence, lack of awareness about the consequences. But in the current scenario due to different awareness programmes they got little bit aware about the facts thus using dustbin a for the waste disposal. In the Market nagar slum every household is using dustbins and even municipal vehicles are also carrying their waste.

Using the toilet shows how much one is aware about cleanliness. This study compared the before-after scenario of the % of people availing toilet facilities. Before only the Market nagar slum had toilet facilities for every household whereas Tala sahi slum didn't have any. In the present context the Tala sahi slum still doesn't have a toilet facility. In the other three slums the percentage of people using toilets has increased due to the implementation of the SBM policy.

If we observe the after and before scenario of the type of cooking fuel being used by people we can see that the majority of people in each slum are using wood and cow dung for cooking. The usage of LPG has increased due to government PMUJ programs which provide LPG and LED bulbs to households.

Before, the majority of people in each slum were using kerosene as their source of light whereas the after scenario presents a different picture: the number of households are using led bulbs as their source of light. Whereas in talasahi slum still every household is using kerosene and in Markat nagar slum every household is using LED bulb as their source of light.

Before the majority of people in each slum except Markat nagar didn't have the electricity facility. But in the recent scenario due to the PMUJ scheme many people are using electricity. But the condition of the Tala sahi slum remains the same, which means it is the worst in every situation.

Table 5: Health profile of the sample households

Slum code	Name of the disease	Occurrence of illness
GA-1	Fever, cold	Occasionally
DE-2	diarrhoea	Frequently
BI-3	Fever	Occasionally
TA-4	Malaria, diarrhoea, jaundice	Very frequently
MA-5	Fever, respiratory problem	Occasionally

Source: Field survey

The study discussed the physical environment change in the context of after and before scenarios. Besides Tala sahi slums in the other four slums the environment has been changed, not fully but partially. We can observe from Table-5, in Tala sahi slum the situation is worse. And, the main problem of this slum is that there is no proper coordination between the people, they are not aware about sanitation and even they don't want that also. Basically, in slums the sources of awareness are provided by various NGOs, govt agencies. The Tala sahi slum and bidanasi slum are not aware about the sanitation. Whereas in Gadagadia slum people are quite mature they understand the consequences of dirt thus they try to improve their conditions on their own. And, as one of the most advanced slums of Cuttack, the Markat nagar slum is in quite a better position if we take into consideration cleanliness.

Table 6: Comparison of Socio-Economic Parameters among sample slums

Items	Slum-1	Slum-2	Slum-3	Slum-4	Slum-5
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean
Annual income	24850*	41100*	39000*	19600*	53525.1*
Food expenditure	385*	615*	645*	230*	345*
Edn. expenditure	-62.5	-263*	-105*	-72.55*	615.05
Health expenditure	-100*	-30	NA	170	150

* Significant at 1% per cent level of significance

In the Table-6, four variables have been considered i.e. annual income, food expenditure, education expenditure and health expenditure. For Slum-1, when we compare the before and after scenario of annual income the mean average of the income is Rs.24850 and it is significant. Now coming back to the mean average of food expenditure, it is of Rs.385 and this data is also significant. But in terms of educational expenditure and health expenditure the previous scenario is higher than the recent. Thus, the mean average is negative. Which is a good thing as the expenditure on health and education declines, this is due to the government policies. In the case of Slum-2, the annual income, food expenditure and education expenditure are significant. The mean average of annual income, food and education expenditure are Rs.41100, Rs.615, and Rs.263 (negative). The minus sign of educational expenditure indicates that expenditure on education was higher before than now. When we talk about the Slum-3 the average mean of annual income is Rs.39000, which means the annual income increased in the present scenario than before. And, the data is significant. Likewise, in food expenditure the average mean is Rs.645 and it is statistically significant. In Slum-4, both the annual income and food expenditure are significant. The mean average of annual income is Rs.19600 whereas, average food expenditure is Rs.230. The health expenditure is high in present scenario but it is not significant. Similarly, in Slum-5, both the food expenditure and annual income are significant. Average annual income is Rs.53525 whereas, average of food expenditure is Rs.345. Here, in the slum four all the four variables are higher in the present scenario than before. Thus, the result of the mean average is positive.

Additionally, the Table-7 illustrated a comparison of listed socio-economic profile including availability of potable water considering all the sample slum units altogether. From the table we found that, the expected distance for bringing water the mean average of all other four variables are high in recent scenarios. And, the

data are significant in case of annual income, food expenditure and distance covered for bringing water in all the five slums.

Table 7: Comparison of Socio-Economic Parameters of slums

Items	Mean
Annual income	35615*
Food expenditure	444*
Education expenditure	22.4
Health expenditure	38
Distance of water sources	-794*

* Significant at 1% per cent level of significance

Distance of water sources in meters

VII KEY FINDINGS

Slums vary in size in terms of both area and number of households. The majority of people belong to the family size of 3-5 in all the five slums. From the study it is found out that in slums majority of people belong to the nuclear family type. In 2 out of 5 slums all the households are of nuclear family types. All the households in the five slums belong to the BPL category. That's because in slum their economic conditions are very vulnerable. From the study we found out that the proportion of male is higher than the females in the slums. 4 out of 5 slums have less than 50 per cent female population in one slum the proportion of male and female are the same i.e. 50 per cent. Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of 35-55 years. In the Gadagadia slum, 10 per cent of households are Christian and the rest 90 per cent are Hindu. In the other four slums the total population are Hindu. There is dominance of OBC category in the four slums i.e. all the sample households are coming under OBC category. And in Gadagadia slum 100 per cent people belong to the ST Category. From the above survey it is found out that the majority of the population are married followed by the unmarried category in all the five slums. Markat Nagar slum is in a better position than the other four slums, where 60% of people from the total population are degree holders and only 5 per cent people are illiterate. And the tala sahi slum has the lowest literacy rate where 50 per cent of households are illiterate. What we found out from the study is that the majority of the population migrated to the slum areas due to job opportunities followed by providing a better future to their children. Some of the slum dwellers migrated because of the exploitation of their respective landlords and some to avail better environment. In the deer park slum 90 per cent of the households migrated to the slum for job opportunities. From the study it is observed that Markat Nagar slum, before there were 30 per cent labourer 50 per cent house maid and 20 per cent *kuli* from the total sample households. Now after the implementation of NULM they got more job opportunities and got engaged in occupations like house painter, carpenter etc. besides this slum in other four slums the occupational status has also increased. The implementation of schemes like AMRUT & PMAY has improved the housing conditions of the slum. 35 per cent huts and 65 per cent kutch houses to 100 per cent of pucca houses are available by tala sahi people. Earlier the majority of people were depending upon wells and rivers as a source of water. But in the recent scenario the municipality is providing water to some households. Where 45 per cent and 75 per cent of people are using municipality water. There is no drainage facility in tala sahi slum. In other slums the percentage of having drainage facilities has significantly increased. Majority of people dispose of the waste in front of the house and in the river. But in the current scenario people using the dustbin for the waste disposal even municipal vehicles are also carrying

their waste. Recently the percentage of people using toilets has increased due to the implementation of the SBM policy. But still in the tala sahi slum people don't have toilets. Majority of people in each slum are using wood and cow dung for cooking i.e. more than 60 per cent of the people. And in recent scenarios the number of households using LPG gas. When we talk about the food intake of the household's majority of people in each slum are consuming rice. In tala sahi slum rice is consumed by every household. Earlier except market nagar no one slums had access to electricity. Even now Majority of people in each, about 60 per cent except Markat nagar, don't have the electricity facility. But in the recent scenario due to the PMUJ scheme many people are availing electricity. Asset details of the households have increased than before. That's because of increased economic conditions. People are able to have different assets. We can observe that the average of each household income has increased than before and that's because of employment programmes provided by the government. From all these analyses we can see that the economic conditions of households are improving. Average annual family income in the previous and recent scenario. Where it can be observed that the average family income of every household has increased. That's because people are engaged in different occupations to improve their household conditions. We can see there is a significant increase in expenditure compared to earlier situations. But when we talk about the health expenditure it's quite low and free in some slums. That's due to the free medical services provided by the government. While observing about the occurrence of diseases the slums are in quite vulnerable condition because there were very frequent occurrences of illness. But in the recent scenario the conditions improved not fully but partially. From the study it is observed that in Tala sahi slum the immunisation status is very low with 20 per cent only. Whereas in Market nagar and in Gadagadia and in Market nagar slum the immunisation status among people is 80 per cent. In the Markat Nagar slum out of total households in that area a huge 60 per cent of women visited hospital for ANC, and in Bidanasi slum 15 per cent of women visited ANC. The main problem of the Tala sahi slum is that there is no proper coordination between the people, they are not aware about sanitation and even they don't want that also. Thus, the physical environment is the worst in that area. The Tala sahi slum and Bidanasi slum are not aware about the sanitation. Whereas, in Gadagadia slum people are quite mature they understand the consequences of dirt thus they try to improve their conditions on their own. And as one of the most advanced slums of Cuttack, the Markat nagar slum is in quite a better position if we take into consideration cleanliness. From the above table it can be observed that that Market nagar slum is in a better position than others as it is benefitted by all the given programmes implemented by the government. The Tala sahi slum only got the housing facility by the AMRUT scheme. We can observe that in the recent scenario the conditions of employment opportunities have improved than before. But that's in the case of male population only. Here the employment opportunity, availability of working days has increased in the case of male population only. The study finds that the low level of household income resulting in Poverty, low level of health and educational facilities and environmental degradation are the major problems of the slum dwellers, which keep them in a vicious cycle.

VIII POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The first and foremost problem that should be addressed is education. Because when one is educated he/she can be aware of others and will contribute to society. The government should take some rigorous effort by providing different

advertisements and educational programmes. The provision of employment on a permanent basis might help the people improve their condition to a great extent. More and more employment opportunities should be created for the rural poor to control the migration to urban areas. More emphasis should be given on the health and educational conditions.

IX LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Generating data required for the analysis and going with any planned design of research of slum people are indeed a stupendous task, as the individual respondents are illiterates and even may not cooperate to collect data by interview as they may not recognize the importance of such studies further, variables related to socio-economic conditions of any community are several, but only a few of them are considered here in this study. Nevertheless, the present study provides a meaningful thumbnail sketch of slum dwellers and as this study is only confined to 100 households only we will not get a clear picture about the slum area inhabitants.

X CONCLUSION

Analysis of the socio-economic conditions of the slum dwellers indicates that their standard of living is low. Slum dwellers are quite aware of the harmful effects of environmental pollution and staying in unhygienic conditions on their health. Their expectations in the city would be fulfilled with regard to employment and earning. The socioeconomic conditions of any group would reflect their standard of living. In spite of the fact that they are in an urban area, they are deprived of various basic facilities to maintain a normal standard of living with lack of housing and other facilities makes their life miserable and never open for improvement. From this study, we observed that the economic condition of the slum dwellers are improving but health and educational status are in measurable condition. However, they expect those problems to be taken by the government and other agencies instead of themselves taking possible care to maintain cleanliness in the surrounding. Lack of basic amenities and their social conditions are the major hindrances to their improvement, in spite of the economic opportunities in the cities. Any plan for slum improvement, therefore, needs to consider these aspects in priority. Social issues may be taken care both by government and non-government in collaboration. However, it is a long run process.

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